

VALKYRIES

Consultation Strategy

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1. Executive Summary

The VALKYRIES project is committed in analysing, improving, and developing infrastructures, protocols and raising data exchange standardisation and harmonisation tactics able to increase the effectiveness and interoperability in emergency situations, such as those prevailing in operation of first aid vehicles or cross-frontier disaster response.

Transversely to the different work packages outlined in the project, acquiring the vision from external experts plays a pivotal role, as it will lead to drive the harmonization of protocols and technologies consistently with the project objectives. To this end, the clear identification of key external stakeholders and the strategies to approach them efficiently emerges as a critical success factor for the project, ensuring a smooth alignment with the innovation priorities across different sectors of the society. It brings into stage the proper definition of a methodology to acquire feedback from external stakeholders considering the selection of appropriate tools and methods upon which the consultation process will rely on. In addition, a preliminary plan to carry out consultation should be presented. Consequently, the presented deliverable seeks to meet the following objectives:

- Define an overall strategy to conduct VALKYRIES' consultation activities.
- Identify key external stakeholders to address the project goals.
- Elaborate a data gathering methodology to acquire stakeholders' feedback.
- Outline a consultation plan to approach external stakeholders throughout the project.

The consultation strategy will work hand in hand with the dissemination and exploitation strategies as well, pursuing the same vision about the targeted external stakeholders and the planification to approach them. Thereby, and due to the tight integration with dissemination and exploitation, the present consultation strategy opens the gate to be enhanced in response with the project priorities, in line with the continuous improvement process it claims. The latter, stressing the fact that the consultation process is not a single-step process but a continuous endeavour to monitor the stakeholders' views across the time as it will be explained in the forthcoming sections of this document.

2. Consultation Strategy

The VALKYRIES Consultation Strategy has the purpose of designing an effective and efficient consultation, building on the overall mapping of available and needed information, being fed through a structured selection of relevant sources, involving the development of constructive, productive relationships with stakeholders throughout the project lifecycle.

VALKYRIES Consultation Strategy ensures all relevant information is considered in such a way that data should be consistently collected from stakeholders upon criterion of reasonable terms. This proposed Consultation Strategy is based on the European Commission’s tool for consulting and requirements gathering, adapted to fit the outcomes of the project.

2.1. Consultation Stages

VALKYRIES builds a Consultation Strategy that can be discretised into four distinct steps shown in Figure 2-1. It can be ongoing or iterative, a one-off consultation related to a specific discrete issue, or a series of consultations related to a particular project.

Figure 2-1- VALKYRIES Consultation steps

2.1.1. Planning

This stage is committed with setting out the aims and specific objectives towards the consultation to be conducted. Planning should be analysed taking into consideration the VALKYRIES stakeholders’ views in order to maximize the effectiveness of the approached process. Key personnel, availability of resources and time constraints shall be considered, and any prior requirement to start the consultation as well. Planning stage addresses the following topics:

- **Objectives and motivation:** Pushed by intrinsic motivations, external requirements, or contractual commitments, the aims and objectives pursued by the consultation shall be clearly stated.
- **Targeted stakeholders:** The identification of the proper stakeholders is of prominent importance as determining their availability or reachability requirements may affect the consultation rollout. Upon identification, in order to approach stakeholders, the design of tailored tools and methods for data acquisition needs to be considered. Awareness of inter-cooperation or engagement constraints should also be borne in mind to avoid potential conflicts of interest.
- **Identification of resources:** Human, capital, or operational resources are going to be consistently planned to reach the selected stakeholders. This may raise additional requirements not previously estimated.
- **Work plan:** The consultation process shall be documented and, thus, provide enough insights on the calendarization, use of resources and expected outcomes. Restrictions for data access or dissemination limitations should be identified as well.

The method of consultation will need to be identified, balancing the resources available and the level of feedback required. The final selection of the stakeholders that will be consulted and methods that will be applied is to be made in the early stages of VALKYRIES.

2.1.2. Process

Corresponds with the “doing” stage which involves the effective execution of the consultation based on the planned sketched in the previous step. The Process stage addresses the following topics:

- **Application of tools and methods:** This is where effective data collection from VALKYRIES stakeholders is carried out. It pursues the effective and accurate translation of the stakeholders’ views into consultation data.
- **Timing and resources:** With the aim to establish effective relationships with stakeholders, the consultation shall follow the timing and resources allocation estimated in the Planning stage, with awareness of existing dependences or blocking situations that may lead to interfere the regular course of actions.
- **Facilitators:** This refers to situations where it is not possible to approach VALKYRIES stakeholders directly, so the need of intermediate facilitators comes into equation to allow a smooth development of the consultation.
- **Two-way communications:** During consultation in VALKYRIES, stakeholders are not only performing as information providers but they are also being informed about whether the consultation is being performed as expected.
- **Storing/recording data:** The consortium shall inform the stakeholders how the collected information will be stored in conformance with principles of reasonable use and with prior consent.

2.1.3. Presentation

Presentation stage addresses the analysis and the reporting of the collected data. The data will need to be analysed and reporting prepared for the relevant audiences, for instance, to the European commission or back to the stakeholders. The form of reporting will need to consider the target audiences and ensure the highest possibility of actions. Presentation should address the following topics:

- **Data analysis:** Objective assessment shall be conducted upon the information collected from VALKYRIES' stakeholders.
- **Presentation of results:** A comprehensive presentation must be ensured when reporting to the desired audiences with a two-fold purpose: transmitting the stakeholders' views clearly enough and pointing out the main findings from the assessment. Graphs and tables shall be the preferable choice when possible.
- **Preparation of reports:** The presentation criteria shall be expressed in consultation reports. It is important in VALKYRIES to agree on the dissemination level the consultation reports must have, to avoid possible situations of unintended data disclosing issues.
- **Reporting back to stakeholders:** Entails the final step of Presentation when the results are formally delivered to the interested parties.

2.1.4. Promise

Promise is the final stage of the consultation strategy and relates to actions emerged as a result of the consultation. The main goal is the engagement with stakeholders in longer-term relationships in the sake of mutual benefit and trust. Promise is also a potential bound to liaison initiatives in VALKYRIES with other European projects and standardization bodies. The Promise stage addresses the following topics:

- **Use the feedback:** Rather than only performing a conscious reporting of results, a deeper understanding of the stakeholders' feedback should fuel actions in the consortium as continuous improvement is a core element of VALKYRIES consortium.
- **Monitoring stakeholders' views:** Considering the dynamic nature of the events, stakeholders' views should be monitored over time as new societal changes can influence the initial consultation goals and stakeholders' priorities, so requiring adaptation to the alternative courses of action is mandatory. The COVID-19 crisis is a good example of this situation.
- **Expression of value of the feedback:** Stressing the need to communicate how valuable the stakeholder's involvement is for VALKYRIES, not only in the call for participation but also in the long-term.
- **Engagement metrics:** Perform a quantitative assessment of the consultation strategy shall lead to point out the outcomes of the process.

Taking this static view of the described consultation framework, the Consortium will thoroughly plan and follow the steps covered in the following cycle, taking into account all the considerations of each phase, and put it to practice iteratively:

Figure 2-2- VALKYRIES Consultation Cycle

A continuous evaluation process will be set in place to adapt and refine the Consultation strategy to the Project specificity and stakeholders, described in Section 3.

2.2. Consultation guidelines

A series of guidelines will be taken into account for the definition of the consultation process and applied to any on-going interaction with stakeholders.

Scope and Objectives. This process will follow the following criteria:

- Mapping the available sources and information in a concrete and topic related way.
- Identify information gaps attainable to be addressed in the consultation process, considering the project lifetime. Determination of the type of information needed, either qualitative or quantitative, should also drive the design of the appropriate methods and tools for the VALKYRIES consortium.
- Decision of the sources of information to be used depending on the topic and related scope of stakeholder involvement. This also entails awareness on the confidentiality requirements.
- Mind sensitive or controversial issues, potential diverging views or high uncertainties which need special attention upon a risk assessment.

Consultation design. The design of the consultation process is about setting the stage to achieve the expectations laid out in the consultation objectives. Selecting the consultation method and tools is a major component of the design, as is ensuring flexibility in the process. When selecting consultation methods and tools, it is important to consider:

- Availability of resources, including human and operational ones. Consider also resources that fall outside the VALKYRIES consortium control.

- Time and skills available from stakeholders to provide the requested data, alongside the type of support (virtual, digital or both).
- Planification over time, which is tightly bound to the objectives and scope of the consultation.
- Prior determination of the stakeholders involved in the consultation process and their level of participation.

Consultation planning. As part of consultation planning, activities are undertaken to determine the level of understanding of the partners, clients and stakeholders on the subject being consulted upon the following considerations:

- Outline different consultations methods for stakeholders and partners, depending on their preferences for consultation methods.
- Documentation and background materials should be provided to stakeholders at the earliest possible time.
- Restrictions to schedule the consultation activities must be stated from the early beginning, and mitigation plans shall be drafted when necessary.

Team roles for the consultation activities. This addresses the following recommendations:

- The VALKYRIES consortium shall balance diverse and complementary skills in areas such as planning, organization, and implementation to drive a proper consultation.
- The team can make recommendations on the type of methods to be used, shall establish reporting relationships, and guarantees specific skill sets.

Importance of a clear communication. It is important for participants to be aware of the following criteria:

- Knowledge of the overall objectives of the consultation for VALKYRIES, and the sub-objectives, if there are any. Clearly defining the objectives of the consultation can reduce the potential for conflict that might arise when participants are left to make assumptions about objectives.
- Participants need to know the objective of consultations and be able to understand the information and documentation they receive. The scope of the decision, how input will be gathered and how it will be incorporated into the decision-making process should be shared.
- The consultation process is documented, including: the participants, how they were consulted, the results of the consultation, and the decisions taken.

Allocation of time. The following topics should be considered:

- Estimating the consultation period is conditioned to weighing the most important factors in terms of complexity, deadlines and resources required for executing the VALKYRIES consultation strategy, identifying activities and milestones at all stages of the process.
- Whether or not they are involved in setting time frames, participants should always be aware of a schedule. This will keep them focused and allow for monitoring throughout the process, as well as for any adjustments that might be required in objectives and plans.
- Consultations will be organized with appropriate timeframes and deadlines so that stakeholders are provided reasonable time to prepare and provide their inputs.

3. Stakeholder mapping

Consultation activities in VALKYRIES are primarily targeted to the groups of stakeholders in accordance with the project objectives. In this section, different players in the stakeholder's ecosystem are identified as a result of a preliminary analysis of their involvement across the project lifetime, and with the expectation to provide continuity to the accomplishments of VALKYRIES in the long-term.

The selection of VALKYRIES stakeholders is driven by the following principles:

- Identify all stakeholder groups relevant for or interested in the policy area concerned.
- Set as prioritized the stakeholder groups which can maximize the level of influence on the initiative to be consulted upon. In this case, experience in relevant projects (either at European or at national/local level) and similar initiatives, as well as active involvement of the stakeholders in communication and dissemination activities related with the policy area concerned, will play a key role in the prioritization. Due to their direct involvement, institutions related to civil protection and emergency care will be highly prioritized, both at the regional / national level and in border countries.
- Identify additional target groups that are in risk of being excluded. Make use of existing stakeholders involved in similar projects, either completed or still running, expert groups, and others.
- Sorting of the identified stakeholders according to their level of interest before undertaking a consultation process. As also mentioned above, relevant experience of the identified stakeholders affects significantly the perception of and the approach towards the policy area concerned and hence the level of interest regarding the consultation process.

3.1. Identification of stakeholders

An initial list of stakeholders who can have a valuable contribution to the VALKYRIES project implementation and at the same time receive meaningful feedback from the outputs of the project has been set-up. The identified stakeholders have been categorized according to the specific sector they represent, considering also their potential contribution in the project consultation goals. This list is non-exhaustive and remains open to update upon consideration of the consortium at any point during the implementation phase of the project.

More specifically, in order to have an adequate representation from the different groups of interest on the stakeholders' map, the Consortium has identified the main target groups consisting of organisations, commercial companies and even individuals who have an interest in or may be affected by the VALKYRIES project.

- **Private Sector:** companies involved in commercializing systems and services for the emergency management, tracking, logistics or support.
- **Research and academia:** the knowledge gained throughout the implementation of the VALKYRIES project should not be restricted to benefit only the consortium but also a wider community of experts; exchanges with other researchers and engineers working on related R&D fields, such as disaster management and disaster actuations (e.g.

activate emergency agencies, practitioners, inform through communication media, etc.) will be of mutual beneficial for all and avoid duplication of efforts.

- **Practitioners:** law enforcement agencies and coordinators during crisis situations and disasters or Humanitarian Organisations (volunteers and professional aid workers). Civil Protection systems, emergency medical services, rescue services, hospital centres, military units for civil protection, police and security services, medical care volunteers, emergency coordination centres...
- **National and international public authorities:** Member States (MS) governments / public administrations, EU and member state policy makers, security and safety service providers and Standardization authorities.
- **Standard, normalization and certification organisms:** organisms to develop and coordinate standards, procedures, guidelines, best practices, minimal codes of practice and similar recommendations), between Member States (MS), Private Sector Members, and Academia Members in the field of security to enhance the safety and resilience of society and in case of Societal and Citizen Security sector including aspects of prevention, response, mitigation, continuity and recovery before, during and after a destabilising or disruptive event.

The following table identifies key stakeholders representing the different target categories. Note that this is not an exhaustive list as it remains open to tailor VALKYRIES objectives across the project lifetime.

Table 3-1- VALKYRIES stakeholders

Category	Representatives
Private Sector	Ambulancias CSA Eliance Helicopter Global Service SL Falck Servicios Sanitarios
Research and academia	SoBigData++ Universities Research centres
Practitioners	SUMMA 112 HOSPITAL DO ESPIRITO SANTO EVORA Spanish Military Emergency Unit (UME) Coastal Administration Centre for Emergency Response Centro Coordinador de Urgencias y Emergencias 112 Extremadura AFCEA Sofia Chapter The International Red Cross and Red Crescent Movement Big Data Value Association (BDVA) European Society for Emergency Medicine International Commission for Alpine Rescue (ICAR) International Life Saving Federation of Europe (ILSE) Disaster Preparedness and Prevention Initiative for South-Eastern Europe (DPPI SEE)

Category	Representatives
National and international public authorities	Spanish Directorate General for Civil Protection and Emergencies (DGPCE) Regional and local authorities involved in civil protection and first Aid Spanish National Cybersecurity Institute INCIBE National and international public authorities Department for Digital Transformation-Presidency of the Council of Ministers (Italy) National Institute of Standards and Technology NIST Hellenic Police / Hellenic Police / Joint Coordination Centre for Operations & Crisis Management Directorate General Joint Research Centre – Commission of the European Communities European Committee for Standardization EU Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid National Civil Protection authority in Bulgaria (DG “Fire Safety and Protection of Population”) Direction of Civil Protection of the Region of Eastern Macedonia and Thrace NATO Centre of Excellence in Bulgaria
Standard, normalization and certification organisms	European Committee for Standardization (CEN) Technical Committee ISO/TC 292, Security and resilience Technical Committee CENTC 391, Societal and Citizen Security ITU-T Study Group 17 – Security, ITU-TSB (Switzerland)

3.2. Engagement strategies

Engaging with the different target audiences will be achieved through the effective combination of the different dissemination tools at the disposal of the consortium.

Stakeholder Engagement is a continuous and systematic process by which an organization establishes a constructive dialogue and a fruitful communication with its key stakeholders. This involvement has a dual purpose. On the one hand such a sharing of knowledge and experience can address both the decision makers’ expectations and the interests of stakeholders, so that the former can take the gathered inputs into account in decision making. On the other hand, a smooth integration of stakeholders in the relevant tasks of VALKYRIES project can support the seamless interaction with project partners and enhance the quality of expected project outputs.

Academic literature, publications from other EU projects and governments’ policy documents identify a variety of effective stakeholder engagement methods, such as online collaborative platforms, online communities, using social media and websites, dialogue and debate, exhibitions and roadshows, public meetings, questionnaires and surveys and establishing an advisory board.

To involve the stakeholders in the project, it is crucial to gain their trust by means of:

- listening to stakeholder concerns.
- understanding and adapting to their needs.

- Familiarizing them with relevant terms, procedures and current practices in place, so that they can fully perceive the context and be able to provide useful input to the project.
- briefing them about expected benefits of the evaluation and of their role within it.

Building trust is especially important to ensure that there is no reluctance (due to ignorance) from the stakeholders about whether and how their input will be used and whether it is valued.

Additionally, it is important that stakeholders completely understand the field of expertise and activity of the organizations that they will interact with, the context and scope of the project and their particular role within this. Building strong relationships and/ or Partnerships with stakeholders will support the effective implementation of the project that can be enhanced and at the same time disseminated through other engagement methods such as online information and social media.

Workshops and exhibitions

Consortium Partners will organize 11 workshops aimed at mobilizing key stakeholders and promoting the exchange of ideas among stakeholders and the scheduling of follow-up actions. It is expected that they will also lead to new business opportunities and related relationships between certification, regulation and standardization entities, end-user groups, academy/RTOs and industry.

Of similar importance is the running of the exhibitions themselves. Industry and other non-scientific conferences are excellent fields to disseminate the project findings and initiate direct conversations with target audiences and stakeholders, particularly events related to namely Disaster Management, Security, Civil Protection, and others. The Consortium aims to foresee speaking slots and co-host VALKYRIES workshops at some conferences. Moreover, the VALKYRIES Consortium will also present project results at fairs, conferences, and congresses to increase awareness and stakeholder engagement.

External Advisory Board

An External Advisory Board (EAB) has been created to obtain independent third-party feedback. It will foster discussions to extract valuable inputs regarding end user requirements, restrictions and limitations, capability gaps, field practices and future needs; research in the field of disaster management; ethical and security preoccupations. The EAB complements the expertise of VALKYRIES partners and will provide feedback to the proposed solutions and contribute to the assessment of the usage cases conducted.

The table below displays members of the EAB:

Table 3-2- VALKYRIES External Advisory Board

Name	Organization	Position	Country
Juan de Dios Pastor Cano	Ambulancias CSA S.L	CEO	Spain
Nikolaos Stefanou	Hellenic Police / Joint Coordination Centre for Operations & Crisis Management	Police Major Senior crisis management expert	Greece

Name	Organization	Position	Country
Konstantinos Chouvardas	Direction of Civil Protection of the Region of Eastern Macedonia and Thrace	Director of Civil Protection of the Region of Eastern Macedonia and Thrace	Greece
José Ignacio Garrote Moreno	Eliance Helicopter Global Service, SL	Training and R & D & I coordinator, medical department	Spain
Eduardo Montero Viñuales	Falck VL Servicios Sanitarios	Director of Development and Communication	Spain
Konstantin Zografov	AFCEA Sofia Chapter	President	Bulgaria
José Rodríguez Gomez	Centro Coordinador de Urgencias y Emergencias. 112Extremadura	Medical Coordinator, Health Sector.	Spain
René Peralta	NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology)	Computer Scientist. Computer Security División	USA
Xiaoya Yang	ITU-T Study Group 17 – Security, ITU-TSB	SG Counsellor	Switzerland

On-line communications, website and social media.

A number of stakeholders will be engaged through both the VALKYRIES project website and Partner websites, which will promote the project concept, its processes and its outputs and outcomes. In addition, social media will be used to engage both the public and other key stakeholders to raise awareness of the project and first aid response at disaster management by emergency health services issues in general. Digital / online and social media are recognised as powerful tools for the promotion and dissemination of information, opinions and ideas to the public although it will, also be vital to recognise that the use of technology or new communication methods poses implementation challenges *per se*. This may be especially relevant within some Partner stakeholder groups, where use of such communication strands could alienate those who do not have access to these technologies.

The interactions and use of tools such as social networking, websites or media tools and other on-line relevant applications, will be monitored to ensure appropriate and ethical use.

Public Events

International, national and regional meetings and conferences offer a large number of opportunities to engage a range of stakeholders including the public, academia, the media, experts in the field etc.

Consortium Partners are drawing up a dissemination plan that will target appropriate events to ensure effective communication of the concepts, processes and outputs of the VALKYRIES project.

4. Data collection methodology

The main objective of data gathering activities of VALKYRIES is to describe the data needs in terms of sources of data including formats, quality, language, need of data models or any consideration that will impact the performance of the system in terms of management of the information and knowledge extraction according to the project needs.

A Data Management Plan (DMP) will include the detailed strategy related to all the data lifecycle to boost openness for research data. In any case, the proposed methodology for public available data gathering considers both secondary methods and primary methods for data collection.

Data collection is divided into six major steps (Figure 4-1): 1) Identification of data gathering needs; 2) Selection and prioritization of data sources; 3) Definition of the data collection plan; 4) Collection; 5) Analysis of the gathered information; and 6) Decision of correction actuations and their enforcement (e.g., prioritize data sources, pre-processing, etc.). These data gathering phases follow a cyclic approach, which will allow to enhance the further collection activities based on the feedback acquired for previous executions and the enforced corrections.

In each step, the ethical-legal compliance will be assessed and monitored according to the type of data processed.

In particular, steps n. 1-3 will be firstly developed in the DMP and updated during the corresponding task, in order to perform a compliant and safe collection and analysis. Organizational and technical measures will be implemented to ensure a responsible development of the data collection methodology and at the same time to better address new challenges and opportunities for the project purposes.

Figure 4-1- VALKYRIES plan for data collection

4.1. Identification of opportunities

During this stage the data needs of the project will be periodically explored or assessed. If the Project Team determines, guided by both automatic and manual procedures, the need for creating or extending some of the considered data collections, the aforementioned cyclic sequence of stages will be initiated. This will also occur if some previously not considered opportunity for enhancing the available data collections is presented, thus aiming on refining the existing information and/or adding alternative points of view. The following properties will serve to assess the need for new data or enhancement opportunities regarding the current available information:

- **Accuracy and Precision:** This characteristic refers to the accuracy of the data. It cannot have any incorrect elements and must convey the correct message without being misleading. This accuracy and precision have a component that relates to its intended use. Without understanding how the data will be consumed, ensuring accuracy and precision could be off-target or more costly than necessary.
- **Legitimacy and Validity:** Requirements governing data set the boundaries of this characteristic. For example, on surveys, items such as gender, ethnicity, and nationality are typically limited to a set of options and open answers are not permitted. Any answers other than these would not be considered valid or legitimate based on the survey's requirement. This is the case for most data and must be carefully considered when determining its quality. On the other hand, data may be corrupt, or forged for misleading the project capabilities.
- **Reliability and Consistency:** Many systems in today's environments use and/or collect the same source data. Regardless of which source collected the data or where it resides, it shall not contradict a value residing in a different source or collected by a different system.
- **Timeliness and Relevance:** There must be a valid reason to collect the data to justify the effort required, which also means it has to be collected at the right moment in time. Data collected too soon or too late could misrepresent a situation and lead to inaccurate decisions.
- **Completeness and Comprehensiveness:** Incomplete data is as dangerous as inaccurate data. Gaps in data collection lead to a partial view of the overall picture to be displayed. Without a complete picture of how operations are running, uninformed actions will occur. It's important to understand the complete set of requirements that constitute a comprehensive set of data to determine whether the requirements are being fulfilled or not.
- **Availability and Accessibility:** This characteristic can be tricky at times due to legal and regulatory constraints. Regardless of the challenge, though, individuals need the right level of access to the data in order to perform their jobs. This presumes that the data exists and is available for access to be granted. On the other hand, real-time observations on the operational environment may be object of technical issues, like Denial of Services (DoS) attempts or latency related problems.
- **Granularity and Uniqueness:** The level of detail at which data is collected is important, because confusion and inaccurate decisions can otherwise occur. Aggregated, summarized and manipulated collections of data could offer a different meaning than the data implied at a lower level. An appropriate level of granularity must be defined to

provide sufficient uniqueness and distinctive properties to become visible. This is a requirement for operations to function effectively.

4.2. Select opportunities and set goals

Based on the needs and opportunities identified at the previous stage, the main purpose of this phase is to solve priority issues and/or opportunities for collecting data, and then setting the required data collection goals and objectives, where:

- **Goals** are general guidelines that explain what the Consortium want to achieve at further gathering actions linked to the issues preliminarily identified.
- **Objectives** define strategies or implementation steps to attain the identified goals. Unlike goals, objectives are specific, measurable, and have a defined completion date. They are more specific and outline the “who, what, when, where, and how” of reaching the goals.

The specific goals and objectives to be defined through the project for each issue and/or opportunity may depend on a hypothesis or guess about what is happening that can be tested using data collection techniques and analysis. With this in mind, the objectives will be chosen or developed with the intention of generating measurable targets/KPIs to monitor their performance. This means that objectives shall have some measurable aspects, even when they are expressed in very broad terms. The process of formulating objectives will be iterative, refining objective statements through rounds of analysis, feedback and input. The final version (or iteration) will reflect a process in which proper consideration has been given to the cost-benefit trade-offs. The objectives of the project will be formulated as expressions that describe particular outcomes in terms of data gathering, being linked to preliminary stated goals. **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** illustrates an example of data gathering action register:

Table 4-1- Data Gathering action register

Action considerations	Description
Objective	Gather external feedback about a particular VALKYRIES requirement for verifying the preliminarily Consortium assumptions.
KPIs	Process:
	Inputs:
	Output:
	Outcomes:
Target	Get Significant feedback (7+) that allow to verify/refuse the assumption within a tolerable cost margin (less than 6 person/hour).
Dates	Start/end
Final results	What is the final result(s) of the data gathering related with the objective declared

4.3. Approach and methods

The methods and approaches for achieving the settled goals will vary significantly depending on a number of factors, including the complexity of the targets, the available resources, data sources selected, etc. During the project execution, each decision of the best suitable methods will explicitly ask the following questions, which will be properly registered at the Data Gathering Report:

4.3.1. Determine the type of data to be collected

Answering this question requires to preliminarily decide the data nature: qualitative or quantitative. Both approaches, while distinct, can overlap and rely on the other to produce meaningful data, analysis and results. The following considerations will be taken into account:

Qualitative Data. Typically, data is called “qualitative” if it is in the form of words but may also include any information that is not numerical in form, such as photographs, videos and sound recordings. Qualitative data excels at “telling the story from the participant's viewpoint” (it helps participants feel like they have been heard), but depending on the nature and size of the project, as well as the sophistication of the methods and analysis used, can take a significant amount of time, be very labour-intensive, and yield results that may not be general enough for policy-making and decision-making purposes.

Quantitative Data. Typically, data is called “quantitative” if it is in the form of numbers. A quantitative approach can be used to count events, metrics or numerical KPIs directly gathered from the operational environment. Common quantitative tools include surveys, questionnaires and statistical data. Quantitative data is perceived to be more credible and reliable than qualitative, which are seen as an objective data source. However, a focus on numbers and rankings alone can overly simplify or lead to an inaccurate understanding of complex situations and realities, unless a broader context is provided.

4.3.2. Consultation Tools and techniques

Qualitative and quantitative data are generally gathered from more than one source. Throughout the project development, if possible, at least two of the following sources should be used together to strengthen reliability and consistency in results.

Pre-existing or official data. Pre-existing or official data is information that has already been documented (e.g., newspaper clippings, case law, photographs) or is created by an organization during its routine business operations (e.g., employee personnel files, student registration forms, annual reports, occurrence reports). The proper organizational and technical measures will be implemented to ensure the ethical-legal compliance of the participation activities (eg., Information sheet, informed consent, privacy information will be prepared and adapted to each context according to the EU and national regulatory framework)

Pros:

- It is efficient. Avoids the time, energy, expense and disruption involved in collecting data as a separate step from running daily operations.

Cons:

- To be a useful source of information, it needs to be collected in a consistent way in time, hence organizations need to be willing to collect the data as part of their ordinary record-keeping procedures or as specific reports.
- The reliability of this data will depend on the diligence and accuracy of the reporting done by the people collecting it.
- Data from scientific literature. Many scientific data are available on specific database (e.g. pub med, Medline, Ovid, Cochrane library...).

Pros:

- It is efficient and reliable. Data from scientific publication are verified and revised accurately.

Cons

- To be a useful source of information this data must be correctly interpreted.
- Some scientific databases are not open source and should be accessed upon paid subscription.

Survey data. Survey research is a broad area and generally includes any measurement procedures that involve asking respondents questions. A "survey" can range from a short paper-and-pencil questionnaire to in-depth interviews.

Pros:

- Very useful for documenting an individual's perceptions and perceived experiences of an organization's work culture, service delivery or other areas of interest.

Cons:

- Quality and reliability of survey data depends on factors like the expertise of the people conducting them, the structure and appropriateness of the questions asked, and the credibility of the methods used to analyse and interpret the results. Therefore, the outputs are prone to subjectivity.
- May not provide an accurate measure of how others perceive a person's background or experience.

Focus groups. In focus groups, the interviewer facilitates the session. A select group of people are brought together, asked questions, encouraged to listen to each other's comments, and have their answers recorded. The same set of questions may be used for a number of different groups, each of which is constituted slightly differently, and for a range of purposes.

Pros:

- Focus groups allow for multiple narratives to be voiced in one "interview" about a research topic of interest.
- Act as tools for education because discussion among participants can illuminate the participants' and the researcher's views, helping to further refine research about a particular topic of interest.

Cons:

- Does not allow participants to fully express their individual opinions and narratives, or ask questions when they immediately come to mind, because of the need to hear and accommodate other voices.
- Persons in the focus groups that are more reluctant / less familiar to express themselves to a wider public may remain (more) silent, if not encouraged to participate more actively by an experienced interviewer and if not much inspired from the conversation as it evolves.

Interviews. Typically, interviews involve a set of standard questions being asked of all respondents, on a one-on-one basis, so that accurate trends and gaps can be drawn from the data. Interviews are commonly conducted face-to-face, but for more rapid results, can also be done over the telephone, or, as technology advances, through video-conferencing and other means.

Pros:

- The interviewer generally has the opportunity to probe more deeply or ask follow-up questions than when in a focus group setting.
- Data from both focus groups and interviews can provide valuable context for understanding and informing research, numbers, events, behaviour and other research goals.
- Depending on the purpose of the data collection, the internal expertise available and other factors, focus groups and interviews can be done with relatively little expense.
- Interviews make it easier to retrieve relevant information from persons that are not familiar to interacting with representatives from scientific consortia and sharing with them their knowledge and experience

Cons:

- One-on-one interviews allow for just one narrative or perspective on a research topic of interest.
- Can be very time consuming and resource intensive.
- Interviewers, in both individual and focus group settings, may distort an interview by not, for example, asking questions that make them uncomfortable or not listening carefully to respondents on topics that they have strong opinions on.

Observed data. Trained staff or external experts can gather data by identifying and recording the characteristics and behaviour of research subjects through observation, either within or outside of an organization.

Pros:

- An effective and capable observer can provide an objective third viewpoint on what is going on and draw out implications that are not obvious or that people are unaware of.
- Can be relatively inexpensive, depending on factors like goals, organization's resources and the duration of gathering activity.

Cons:

- An observer, either specially trained or not, may not always be accurate.

4.3.3. Data retention policies

Through the project implementation, data shall be collected and analysed on a short-term or project basis in response to situations or needs that arise from time to time. A short-term data collection project would include a start and a due date, with predefined deliverables to be carried out over a certain period of time. In these grounds, the best practice will be to collect data on an ongoing, permanent basis, and to analyse these data as often as needed to identify, address and monitoring barriers. Data collected in a time-limited study may be less complete than data collected through ongoing monitoring, but they will be particularly required at the first analytical actions of the project (mostly in Work Packages 1 to 6). This is because short-term studies do not allow for the assessment of trends, patterns or changes over time. However, where costs, time, ethical-legal framework, and resources are a factor, short-term studies may be the preferred choice to fulfil a need and project goals, thus directly aiming on support the VALKYRIES requirements definition and decide upon the most suitable design approaches.

4.4. Data collection

Based on the decisions taken during the previous stages, the targeted information will be gathered. Since this process may require considerations regarding the data source, type and selected procedures, the following general considerations will be taken into account.

- Determining who will collect the data (e.g., experts or trained employees).
- Identifying the logistics, resources, technology, and people needed to develop and implement a data collection initiative.
- Anticipating and addressing key stakeholder concerns and questions about the project and the data usage.
- Designing a communication and consultation strategy that will explain the data collection initiative and encourage the highest possible participation rate.
- Protecting privacy and personal information by using carefully controlled procedures for collecting, storing and accessing data, after an impact assessment.
- Minimizing the impact and inconvenience for the people involved, which includes agreeing upon the best time and location to collect the data.
- Aiming for flexibility to allow for changes without great expense or inconvenience during the data collection processes.

4.5. Analysis and process assessment

Whether quantitative and/or qualitative methods of gathering data are used, the analysis can be complex, or less so, depending on the methods used and the amount of data collected. For example, data directly observed on the operational environment may contain noise or miss fragments. On the other hands, the data sources may be unavailable or not responding as expected. These situations may be registered for allowing decide corrective actions. If the data is observed at the operational environment, it will be transposed into the platform knowledge representation or supported data model, thus being able to feed the platform connectors.

On the other hand, according to the adopted circular data collection methodology, the data managers will decide to act on the data, collect more of the same type or modify the collection approach. The analysis, interpretations and conducted actuations will be registered as feedback for further decisions and analysed as “lessons learnt”. The register will provide the following information:

- A summary of the results of the analysis and interpretation of the data
- Identification of the barriers, gaps and opportunities that exist or may exist when addressing related objectives or applying similar *modus operandi*.
- The steps that will be taken to address these barriers, gaps or opportunities now and in the future.
- Realistic, attainable improvements with short-term and longer-term timelines
- If this is the case, input sought from the project stakeholders and related communities.

In addition, the consultation process shall be evaluated upon the set of performance parameters defined in order to understand how effective the acquisition of data was, and to realize whether the consultation goals have been met.

General directions: full review of the existing norms and regulations applicable to the VALKYRIES case studies. This will ensure the ethical-legal compliance of the project ecosystem. Proper technical and organizational measures will be implemented accordingly.

4.6. Corrective actions

According to the adopted circular data collection methodology, the data managers will decide to act on the data, collect more of the same type or modify the collection approach. The analysis, interpretations and conducted actuations will be registered as feedback for further decisions and analysed as “lessons learnt”. The register will provide the following information:

- A summary of the results of the analysis and interpretation of the data.
- Identification of the barriers, gaps and opportunities that exist or may exist when addressing related objectives or applying similar *modus operandi*.
- The steps that will be taken to address these barriers, gaps or opportunities now and in the future.
- Realistic, attainable improvements with short-term and longer-term timelines.
- If this is the case, input sought from the project stakeholders and related communities.

5. Consultation template

Prior to any consultation interaction with any stakeholder, regardless of the consultation method, a concise report, the outline of which is presented below, will be completed and sent to the participants.

Table 5-1- VALKYRIES Consultation template

<p><u>CONSULTATION OBJECTIVES:</u></p> <p>< Explicit General and specific for each case.></p> <p><Structure and content of the final report/document, minimum expected result></p>
<p><u>BACKGROUND INFORMATION:</u></p> <p>< Identify all necessary information. This knowledge must be considered before participating in the consultation process></p> <p><Necessary prior knowledge to be considered before participating in the consultation process></p>
<p><u>PARTICIPANTS:</u></p> <p><list of stakeholders and other representatives (name, role, etc.)></p>
<p><u>CONSULTATION TOOLS:</u></p> <p>< Description of the tools and techniques to be applied with specific references of the support access information if required></p>
<p><u>RECOMMENDATIONS:</u></p> <p><General and specific recommendations for a successful rollout of the consultation process></p>
<p><u>EXPECTED FINAL RESULTS:</u></p> <p><General and specific results of consultation process expected></p>
<p><u>ORGANIZATION AND PLANNIFICATION PROCESS:</u></p> <p><Personal resources (Leader of the consultation, IT responsible person, general support, etc.)></p> <p><Other resources (Apps, IT tools, data support, etc)</p> <p><Plan and timing. The starting date and the deadline for each part of the consultation process (e.g., Consultation launch, data collection, conclusion report and final document)></p> <p>Ethical committee approval where needed.</p>
<p><u>RISK IDENTIFICATION</u></p> <p>Risk assessment and limitations of the consultation process (IT tools, timing, bank holidays, etc.)</p> <p>risks related to the participation of persons (data protection, informed consent, opt-in/opt-out)</p>
<p><u>SUPPORTIVE MATERIAL:</u></p> <p><Additional supportive material to allow a seamless execution of the process></p>

6. Evaluation and Continuous improvement

After any consultation interaction with a stakeholder, regardless of the consultation method, a concise report, as outlined below, will be sent to the participants for their completion. The consultation template may include the action template for any references, followed by any meeting and consultation notes, and ending with the following short questionnaire shown in Table 6-1.

Table 6-1- Example of VALKYRIES consultation questionnaire

General Questions	
Were objectives of the consultation and expected outcomes identified?	
Were anticipated costs, resources and required skills identified?	
Design	
Were consultations method(s) identified for various circumstances and participants?	
Were participants given enough time to prepare input for consultations?	
Implementation	
Were expectations shared with and among participants?	
Were conflicts anticipated and managed?	
Were participants prepared to participate in activities? Was enough information provided? Was the information understandable?	
Was monitoring incorporated in the consultation process? Were modifications necessary (in methods, timetable, resources or participation) to advance the consultation objectives?	
Synthesis & Reporting	
Was feedback sought on the process and progress of the consultation?	
Was it determined in advance how to report back, when and to whom?	
Was a feedback timetable determined for future interactions?	
Evaluation	
Was there ongoing documentation and reporting throughout the consultation process?	
How was the feedback used in the decision-making process?	
Is follow-up required for next steps in the relationship with participants and stakeholders?	

7. Preliminary consultation plan

The consultation activities planned in VALKYRIES are described in Table 7-1. It is worth stressing the list of activities is not exhaustive as it may accommodate other activities as the project evolves.

Table 7-1- VALKYRIES preliminary Consultation Plan

Activity	Objective	Estimated date	Responsible	Candidate stakeholder
Meeting with External Advisory Board	Regular feedback on progress	M4, M8, M12, M16, M20	VALKYRIES consortium	EAB
VALKYRIES Workshop 1	Present project's status and achievements and get feedback from stakeholders	M6	VALKYRIES consortium	EAB, practitioners, private sector
VALKYRIES Workshop 2	Disseminate outcomes, discuss standardization and exploitation actions	M12	VALKYRIES consortium	EAB, practitioners, private sector, non-profit organizations, Research and academia, National and international public authorities, European Committee for Standardization (CEN), Technical Committee ISO/TC 292, Security and resilience and Technical Committee CENTC 391, Societal and Citizen Security
VALKYRIES Workshop 3	Disseminate the final project outcomes and discuss exploitation opportunities	M24	VALKYRIES consortium	All stakeholders
Ethical-Legal VALKYRIES Workshops	Sensitize ethical-legal framework and discuss protocols	M6, M12, M18, M24	SSSA	All stakeholders

Activity	Objective	Estimated date	Responsible	Candidate stakeholder
Standardization VALKYRIES Workshops	Discuss regulation, standardization, certification and harmonization issues	M6, M12, M18, M24	VALKYRIES consortium	EAB, practitioners, private sector, non-profit organizations, Research and academia, National and international public authorities, European Committee for Standardization (CEN), Technical Committee ISO/TC 292, Security and resilience and Technical Committee CENTC 391, Societal and Citizen Security

7.1. Meetings with External Advisory Boards

Coinciding with some of the Project Steering Team (PST) meetings, a time slot will be reserved to meet with the External Advisory Board and extract inputs regarding the progress of the project and to seek advice on any issues that may have arisen during the period.

Main objective: Discuss and obtain impartial scientific advice and feedback on the progress and results of the project. The feedback obtained from these meetings will be registered and analysed in order to detect potential risks, gaps and corrective actions.

7.2. VALKYRIES workshop 1

The first VALKYRIES workshop will take place at the end of the sixth month, to present the project's status and achievements (requirements, scope of the demonstrators, normalization plans, consultation strategy, terminology and semantics, pre-standardization map, etc.) and receive feedback from stakeholders to improve the impact of the final results, being taken into consideration when designing harmonization tactics and reference integrating the efforts to be conducted.

Main objective: Present the VALKYRIES progress and its current outcomes to VALKYRIES stakeholders. Ask them for feedback and discuss expectations and possible exploitation approaches. The received suggestions shall enhance the VALKYRIES tasks to be conducted, settling the grounds for the rest of the project. The feedback will be compiled and considered in order to detect potential risks, gaps and corrective actions regarding the approach of expectations and exploitation.

7.3. VALKYRIES workshop 2

The second VALKYRIES workshop is scheduled at the end of the first year of the project and will have as main target to disseminate the intermediate project outcomes and discuss the status and expectations from the reference integration; based on them, discuss with the present stakeholders the best suitable standardization and exploitation foreseen actions.

Main objective: Present the intermediate outcomes of the VALKYRIES project to the different groups of stakeholders. Based on that, it will be possible to refine the ongoing reference integration and to enhance the direction of the initiated pre-standardization, standardization and harmonization actions. The feedback will be registered and analysed to detect potential risks, gaps and corrective actions regarding the reference integration and standardization process.

7.4. VALKYRIES workshop 3

The third VALKYRIES workshop is scheduled at the end of the project and will have as the main target to disseminate the final project outcomes, and based on them, discuss with the best and post-project exploitation opportunities.

Main objective: Present the outcomes of the project to stakeholders. Based on that, it will be made possible to better assess the impact in the invited communities and receive feedback about the planned final and post-project exploitation actions. The information obtained shall be recorded and examined to identify potential risks, gaps and corrective actions in the planned impact and post project exploitation.

7.5. Ethical-Legal VALKYRIES Workshops

These workshops will take place each six months and will be organised to sensitize the ethical-legal framework in the VALKYRIES context and to discuss the progress on the development of protocols with stakeholders. The same workshop will be taken in VALKYRIES to reach the most comprehensive number of stakeholders.

Main objective: Disseminate and discuss the VALKYRIES results on the ethical-legal issues and to discuss concrete regulatory solutions to standardisation and interoperability goals regarding data and technology in the field of VALKYRIES disaster management scenarios.

The first one will be held as a panel at the CPDP Conference in Brussels on Jan. 28th 2022 (<https://www.cpdpconferences.org/>).

A summary of the most relevant information will be registered and explored to detect risks, gaps and potential corrective actions regarding the standardisation and interoperability of data and technology.

7.6. Standardization VALKYRIES Workshops

These workshops will take place each six months (coinciding with ethical-legal ones) and will be organized in parallel to the VALKYRIES' ethical-legal, closing the external stakeholders related to regulation, standardization, certification and harmonization to the Consortium activities. Their main targets will be to discuss the opportunities and progress on the actions mentioned above

and getting close to the ongoing/planned Pan-European efforts (institutes, agencies, etc.) and working groups and end-users.

Main objective: Disseminate and discuss VALKYRIES results on the regulation, standardization, certification and harmonization issues towards awareness raising of the project results and alignment with European and International actions.

The feedback will be recorded and studied to identify risks, gaps and required corrective actions to align European and International actions with VALKYRIES results.

8. Conclusions

The purpose of this deliverable is to present the VALKYRIES consultation strategy underpinning the guidelines to drive a consistent gathering and monitoring of the external stakeholders' views regarding the project development. The overall methodology presented here intends to follow a continuous improvement cycle, meaning the acquired feedback and the methodology applied for consulting shall be critically assessed in order to introduce enhancements in further iterations of the consultation process.

Relevant external stakeholders have been identified in accordance with the aims of VALKYRIES spanning across different sectors of the society such as the public authorities both at national and European scale, representatives of the academia, security practitioners, standardization and certification organisms, among other players which are targeted as critical to attain the project goals so as raising the standardisation and harmonisation landscape surrounding first-aid response processes and emergency use cases.

Similarly, the VALKYRIES data collection methodology was presented in detail describing the data needs, key data models, quality expectations, and other considerations that will drive the consultation activities when gathering and processing data key stakeholders. In addition, a preliminary consultation plan has been presented by targeting potential opportunities to approach the external stakeholders and carry out the consultation effectively.

It is worth mentioning that the consultation strategy plan may undergo modifications for better tailoring to other milestones of the project, mainly those related with the communication, dissemination, standardization, and exploitation strategies, along with the data management plan. They all planned to be released at the sixth month of the project.

References

- [1] European Commission. “Better regulation "Toolbox: Stakeholder consultation”. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/better-regulation-toolbox_2.pdf
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- [3] International Standard ISO 22300, Security and resilience - Vocabulary